

Table 2. Resistance to bacterial blight of some rice cultivars grown at sites surveyed in Nepal, 1987-89.

Cultivar	Location	District	Disease reaction ^a
Masuli	Urlabari	Jhapa	MS
	Shibagunj	Jhapa	S
	Ramdaiya	Dhanusa	S
	Janakpur	Dhanusa	HS
	Lahan-6	Siraha	MS
	Hapur	Sarlahi	S
	Hariwan	Sarlahi	S
	Panwanipur	Bara	HS
	Jagamath-7	Parsa	MS
	Jagannathpur	Parsa	MS
	Saradanagar	Chitwan	MS
	Bharatpur	Chitwan	S
	Bhandara	Chitwan	S
	Gaidakot	Nawalparasi	MS
	Tharunagar	Nawalparasi	S
	Sidarthnagar	Rupandehi	S
	Paruwa	Rupandehi	S
	Parsari	Rupandehi	S
	Gularia	Bardiya	HS
	Mahendranagar	Kanchanpur	S
	Bayarghari	Syangja	S
	Raniguan	Tanahu	S
	Sindheshore-6	Sindhuli	MS
CH45	Jamuniya	Dhanusa	HS
	Naktajhil	Dhanusa	S
	Baluwa-9	Bara	HS
	Rampur Tokan	Bara	HS
	Buniyad-3	Bara	HS
	Bhaubari-4	Parsa	MS
	Jagamathpur	Parsa	HS
	Lipani birta-2	Parsa	S
	Lipani birta-10	Parsa	HS
	Himali	Bhjandara	Chitwan
Jorpati		Kathmandu	HS
Dillibazar		Kathmandu	HS
Bhaktapur		Bhaktapur	MS
Battar bazar		Nuwakot	HS
Gauribis		Nuwakot	HS
Sarju 49	Basabasai	Nawalparasi	HS
	Sidarthnagar	Rupandehi	S
	Maduali	Rupandehi	HS
	Parsari	Rupandehi	HS
	Shibapur	Kapilvastu	S
	Bade	Kapilvastu	HS
Bindeshwori	Sunwari	Sunsari	S
	Rampur Tokan	Bara	HS
	Feta-1	Bara	HS
	Liponi Mal	Parsa	HS
	Sindheshore	Sindhuli	HS
Janaki	Belbasi	Morang	S
	Monkapur	Banke	MS
	Mahendranagar	Kanchanpur	HS
	Khampacamp	Nuwakot	MR
Muturi	Simroundard	Bara	HS
	Jagmath	Parsa	HS
	Pokharia	Parsa	S
Laxmi	Padariya	Siraha	MS
	Mahendranagar	Kanchapur	S
IR24	Mahendranagar	Kanchapur	S
	Mahendranagar-16	Kanchapur	S

^a Resistant (R) = no disease symptom in the field, moderately resistant (MR) = plants with less than 10% leaf blighted, moderately susceptible (M) = plants with 10-25% leaf blighted, susceptible (S) = plants with 26-50% leaf blighted, highly susceptible (HS) = plants with more than 50% leaf blighted.

BB-susceptible Masuli was the most extensively grown cultivar in the 23 sites surveyed (Table 2). IR24 was the only IR

cultivar grown (in Kanchanpur district, western Nepal). ■

Timing of insecticide treatment for rice tungro (RTV) control

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We studied the effect of treating the nursery and transplanted seedlings with a combination of knockdown and insectistatic compounds for RTV control, using green leafhopper (GLH)- and RTV-susceptible IR22.

Eight treatments were compared: no insecticide; applying insecticides in the nursery only, at 12 d after seeding (DAS); applying 2 d after transplanting (DT) only; applying 16 DT only; applying in the nursery and 2 DT; applying 2 and 16 DT; applying in the nursery and 16 DT; and applying in the nursery, 2 and 16 DT. Plants were sprayed with cypermethrin at 25 g ai/ha and buprofezin at 500 g ai/ha.

RTV infection in the nursery was determined by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) at 21 and 26 DAS. Groups of seedlings were collected at random from 42 sampling points along the length of the nursery. Each group, averaging 18 seedlings, was tested separately.

Disease transmission by 80 leafhoppers collected in the nursery by insect net at 13 DAS was also tested.

Seedlings were transplanted 26 DAS in 10-m² plots in a randomized complete block design with four replications. RTV infection at 14, 33, and 61 DT was determined by ELISA from 10 samples/plot, sampled in a W-pattern. Each sample consisted of 16 hills.

Seedlings from the untreated nursery at 21 DAS showed 4% infection by rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) alone and 7% infection by rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) done; seedlings from the treated nursery had 2% infection by RTBV alone. AT 26 DAS seedlings from the treated nursery had 2% infection by RTBV alone; those from the untreated nursery had 2% infection by RTSV alone.

No GLH were collected in the treated nursery 13 DAS. GLH were collected in

the untreated nursery but no viruliferous insects were found among 80 tested.

RTV infection at 14 DT did not vary greatly among treatments (see figure). At 33 DT, lower infection of RTBV + RTSV was found in plants treated at 2 and 16 DT and in plants treated in the nursery and at 2 and 16 DT.

More significant differences in infection were observed at 61 DT. Infection in plants treated at 2 and 16 DT and those treated in the nursery and at 2 and 16 DT did not differ.

Insecticides applied during the first 2 wk after transplanting slowed RTV development, resulting in a lower level of infection even 61 DT. Insecticide application in nurseries may not be economical because there was no appreciable difference in infection between untreated seedlings and those treated in the nursery. ■

Infection of RTBV and RTSV assayed by ELISA in IR22 plants at different days after transplanting after insecticide treatments in the nursery, and at 2 and 16 DT. IRRI, 1990.

Effect of wet-dry cycles on sclerotial weight and viability of *Sclerotium hydrophilum*

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Sclerotium hydrophilum Sacc. causes rice stem rot. The fungus survives through sclerotia, which are subjected to different field conditions. We studied the effect of alternate wet-dry cycles on sclerotial weight and viability.

Sclerotia produced on rice grain-hull medium were separated, washed, and their surface water absorbed with blotters. The moisture content of the freshly harvested sclerotia was 20.5%.

These sclerotia were dried in the shade at room temperature (26-37 °C) for 24 h. Their moisture content was reduced to 11.7%.

Six dishes containing 1,000 mg dried sclerotia each were wet for 24 h by adding 20 ml water to each dish. Then they were dried in shade for 24 h, for each wet-dry cycle. One set of six dishes was given no treatment. Three dishes in each set were used to measure weight, and three to measure viability.

1. Effect of wet-dry cycles (WD) on sclerotial weight in *Sclerotium hydrophilum*.

Sclerotia weight and viability of both treated and untreated sets were measured after each wet-dry cycle. For viability, sclerotia were surface sterilized with 0.05% H₂OCl₂, plated on 2% water-agar amended with 1,000 ppm streptomycin, and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C for 3 d. The wet-dry cycles continued until scler-

rotial weight became constant. After the last cycle, moisture content of untreated sclerotia was 11.3%; that of sclerotia subjected to wet-dry treatment was 11.5%.

At first, sclerotia weight was reduced sharply with wet-dry treatment to about half (490 mg) by completion of the third